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Challenges And Opportunities Of Engaging Women In Rural Development Programmes In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Rural development remains a challenge in Nigeria, and the exclusion of women in rural development programmes in Nigeria continues to have maximum impact on development prospect of the Nigerian economy. The aim of the paper was to assess the challenges and opportunities of engaging women in rural development programmes in Nigeria. The methodology adopted for the paper is the descriptive qualitative method of secondary sources. The assessment of existing literatures on the subject provided insight on the situation of women as regards the challenges they face in rural development. The paper found that agricultural and animal husbandry and production, providing food, water, and fuel for the family, as well as other livelihood tasks, are just a few of the diverse experiences that rural women possess in Nigeria. A significant obstacle to the contribution of rural women to development is the lack of fundamental social, economic, and physical infrastructure. Rural women are severely disadvantaged because they lack essential infrastructures like telephones, a good road network, power supply services, and water and sanitation facilities. Women suffer from poverty, lack of empowerment, and abuse of all kinds as a result of these obstacles. Bold policy, legal, legislative, and administrative measures, as well as reforms, are necessary to remove these obstacles and provide the opportunities for women to contribute to not only rural but national development.

Keywords: Women, rural, development, culture, challenges

INTRODUCTION

Globally, national, regional, and international governments and non-governmental organisations have placed a high priority on developing rural communities. Due to certain structural and cultural quirks, different nations have distinct strategies. The majority of developed and industrialised nations rely on the neoliberal strategy, which attracts rural growth from the outside through "trickle down" processes caused by increased capital output in rural regions (Blakely, 2009, O Toole & Macgarvey 2013). In this case, tax breaks, the construction of vital infrastructure, and other public spending initiatives are used to draw capital production to rural areas. This market-based strategy for rural development frequently prioritises rural expansion over actual development (Wolman & Spitzley, 2016). As a result, the neoliberal development strategy in rural areas rarely places issues of social justice, environmental concerns, and human capital enhancement at its centre. Rural residents are rarely encouraged to participate and be inclusive by such a development trajectory (Piore, 2015).

A rural development strategy that excludes the involvement of rural residents is nevertheless exploitative. In developing nations with low levels of infrastructure and human capital and significant levels of gender discrimination, the issue of inclusive and participatory development at the rural level is particularly

crucial. According to the research, for example, women control the vast majority of informal activity in rural economies in emerging and impoverished nations. Although rural women engage in a variety of creative endeavours, the mainstream public development agenda never takes into account their contributions. According to a 2015 study conducted in India by Gopinath and Kalra, women are generally engaged in domestic work, farming, and other community-related activities. According to various studies, women in sub-Saharan Africa produce almost two-thirds of food crops and, depending on the region, make up 60–90% of the agricultural work force (Pala, 2016; Ogunlela & Mukhtar 2009).

Despite being the fundamental pillar of rural development in underdeveloped nations, women are not represented in the majority of rural development policies and initiatives. Although women enable the numerous productive and development activities essential to human well-being, they are not formally regarded as a component of the traditional economy (Brandt, 2015). According to O Toole and Macgarvey (2013), who cited Waring (2009), the conventional economy encompasses paid labour, business operations, and profit-making, but it has not taken into account women's selfless contributions to the welfare of rural communities. Women's contributions to rural development in Nigeria are primarily found in the unorganized agriculture sector. Nonetheless, women were rarely at the forefront of the development agenda for most government policies and programs. Despite differences in statistics, it is generally believed that women participate in public rural development programs at a very low level (Damisa & Yohanna 2017, Ogunlela and Mukhtar 2009). This study's significance lies in its evaluation of women's organizations involved in rural development in Rivers State through an analysis of certain facets of the state's official rural development policies and initiatives. It is anticipated that the paper will emphasize various obstacles and important policy concerns in order to concentrate on the opportunities and difficulties of involving women in rural development programs.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of the Study is to evaluate the role of women in rural development programmes in Nigeria; while assessing the challenges and opportunities associated with integrating women into policies for rural development.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilised the secondary source of data as well as the document analysis as methodology for the study. The qualitative study is therefore the approach utilised for the study. Data was accessed through existing data base of published articles.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Theoretical Review of Development and Gender Mainstreaming

A common discursive framework for comprehending the connection between women and rural development is gender and development, often known as gender mainstreaming in development (Tavira & Tapia, 2018; Kaur and Sharma, 2011). This trend from the gender and development literatures has helped to define and influence international organisations' essential agendas regarding the execution of programs and policy guidelines over the years. With the ultimate goal of ensuring the quality of men and women, the third UN Millennium Development Goal, which focused on gender equality, is one of the most recent authoritative declarations aiming to establish places for gender mainstreaming in all political, social, and economic arenas.

Following the surge of intellectual rethinking of the "linear," "modernising," and "dependency" paradigm of the concept of development in the 1980s, gender mainstreaming in development concerns developed (Tavira & Tapia, 2018). According to Gardner and Lewis (2003, cited in Tavira & Tapia, 2018), "there is a more frequent tendency to concentrate in specific groups and problems ('women', 'poor', etc.), a more reflective attitude towards help and development, and a new emphasis towards 'bottom-up' and socially organised initiatives" following the abandonment of the generalised and determinist theory." "In this framework, development language and discourses suffer a switch towards concepts that make reference to the plurality of the society," Tavira & Tapia (2018:208) continued. Actors, agents, subjects, and citizens

are discussed, and as a result, governments' and international organisations' practices and discourses swiftly adjusted to the discursive wave and intellectual styles, incorporating conceptual elements from a theoretical work that was framed by a number of social events into their public policies.

Taking into account the role and contribution of women to the development process is part of this paradigm shift. Research on women's roles in particular social and economic activities has grown over the past three decades (Sharma, 2011; Gopinata & Kalra, 2015; Kaur and Sharma, 2011). According to Kaur and Sharma (2011), a higher proportion of these research documented the contributions made by women in both agricultural and non-agricultural sectors. For example, Sharma (2011) documented the great agricultural knowledge of women in animal farming in an investigation of their labour in northern India. In India, women's contributions to domestic, farming, and community-related tasks were documented by Gopinath and Kalra (2015). Mencher (1982) concentrated more on the role that women play in reducing poverty and maintaining the home. According to Kandiyoti (1990), despite exceedingly outdated technology and severely limited time resources, women in sub-Saharan Africa have made significant contributions to rural development in both agricultural and non-agricultural activities. Women's contributions to rural development have been roughly classified as:

- A. Food producers and active agrarian sector participants
- B. Daily household upkeep duties
- C. Small-scale revenue-generating ventures
- D. Overall support for the welfare of their rural neighbourhood.

The role of women in Nigerian rural development can be examined under these areas. Women have been helpful in the agricultural sector in small-scale farming operations that contribute to the food security of households, offer substantial job opportunities, and produce some revenue for other livelihood endeavours. Women have played important responsibilities at many levels when it comes to managing the house. Water fetching, household sanitation, fuel wood gathering, food processing and preparation, child care and raising, and family welfare are all examples of household chores that fall under the purview of women. These are essential for the stability and advancement of families as well as the general growth of the community. The family as a whole has been shown to benefit economically, socially, and nutritionally from women's direct control over income and family resources. In Nigeria, however, how are these translated? This paper's remaining sections aim to evaluate Nigerian rural development techniques with respect to their history, effects, obstacles, and opportunities for women.

The Role of Women in Nigeria's Rural Development Practices

Nigeria's rural areas continue to be incredibly underdeveloped based on systematic investigations and physical measurements. Massive poverty, a lack of social, economic, and physical infrastructure, a lack of human capital development, and the declining position of rural women are some signs of rural underdevelopment. Even after numerous national and regional development initiatives, there is still a significant gap between rural and urban communities (Onokerhoraye, 2018; Olayiwola and Adeleye, 2015). The main indicator of this discrepancy is the growing gaps in standard of living, human development, physical amenities, social possibilities, and quality of life.

Research has sought to explain the inequalities between rural and urban areas. When it came to investments in significant development facilities, Blench (2013) connected these disparities to the British colonial policy of spatial segregation. "In colonial times, access was so problematic and information systems were so underdeveloped that rural citizens could barely articulate even major issues," the author claims (Blench (2013: 7). In rural Nigeria, British colonial interest was typified by two-pronged exploitation. First of all, rural areas were only accessible as primary resource areas for raw material exports. According to the second stage of exploitation, the rural areas were used as food production hubs for the few metropolitan centres that would eventually supply the colonial residents' basic food demands. Every government policy agenda that acknowledges rural areas as the only source of food for urban inhabitants has incorporated this tendency in development thought and practice. It implies that rural communities rely on the agricultural sector for jobs, income, and other means of subsistence. However,

Nigerian rural areas continue to be extremely underdeveloped and neglected in spite of this acknowledgement and their contribution to the country's GDP and economy (IFAD, 2011). The majority of investments in economic, social, and physical infrastructure have gone towards the cities. As a result, the majority of people in rural areas lack access to safe drinking water, and the rural population has very limited access to facilities like schools and health clinics. In Nigeria, rural areas are not desirable places to live because they are linked to poverty.

Young, physically fit male individuals migrate to cities at high rates due to poor access to social and physical infrastructure in rural areas. Rural areas are gradually becoming less populated as a result of migration trends.

According to estimates, 53% of Nigerians lived in rural regions in 2006 (Muoghalu, 2012), and 51.6% of Nigerians lived in rural areas in 2011, according to World Bank data. The fact that women make up the majority of the rural population today and engage in everyday existential and subsistence farming activities is of particular importance. Because of Nigeria's patriarchal social norms, women are consistently viewed as inferior to men, which tends to restrict their access to opportunities and participation in development initiatives. According to Kamar et al. (2014: 26), who cited Amain (2008), "...to reach all the people one has to reach the women." This highlights the significance of involving women in rural development. After you have reached the women, you have reached the children, the family, and the country. You have made your way across the country at the level of the local government, the rural community, the city, the village, the farm, the school, the university, and your home." In what ways do women play a significant role in rural development practices? What opportunities and difficulties exist for include women in rural development initiatives? Which crucial areas should be the focus of state and federal policy to improve women's integration in rural development? The rest portion of this paper addresses these and related issues, specifically mentioning Nigeria.

An examination of the obstacles preventing women from taking part in Nigerian rural development initiatives

Economic disadvantage, fear of political vices, cultural beliefs and value systems, religious teachings and relics, women's femininity and physiological state, and male egocentrism were found to be the most likely obstacles to women's active participation in development programs and politics at the grassroots level in Nigeria. The findings of Adhiamdo-oduol (2013), Farzana (2015), and Joe (2010), which showed that women are weaklings who cannot survive the tough character of the game of politics, are consistent with cultural ideas and value systems as barriers to women's engagement in politics. This supports the conclusion that women's physiological states and femininity disqualify them from taking part in community development initiatives. Economic disadvantage as a barrier to women's involvement in grassroots politics in Rivers State is consistent with Fadeiya (2015), who argued that women lack their own money and that it belongs to their husbands. Given the rising expenses of running a successful election campaign, this presents a significant obstacle for women in developing nations like Nigeria, where they could use their political power to influence development initiatives in rural communities.

Notwithstanding the obstacles to women's involvement in grassroots politics in Nigeria, the impact of women's involvement on community development includes a sense of inclusion in the accomplishment of community goals and objectives, the promotion of policies and programs for women's advancement, and a greater mobilisation of resources and skills for bettering the social and economic circumstances of the community. According to Ugochukwu (2016), women's creative energies must be mobilised for a society free from poverty. According to Adedotun (2010), women's economic empowerment influences how they see themselves and are viewed by the community, providing them with local support for rural development.

Nigeria's Rural Development Plans' Effect on Women's Involvement

From before independence to the current democratic era, numerous state policies and development programs have influenced the growth of Nigeria's rural areas. However, what are such development plans and strategies, and how do they affect women's participation? With programs like Better Life for Rural

Women (1987) and other family-based efforts created specially to raise the status of rural women in development activities, rural women began to receive some attention starting in the late 1980s.

However, Nigeria's democratic trials from 1999 to the present have greatly expanded the opportunities for women to participate in development initiatives. Women's interest in electoral politics was sparked by the democratic participation framework, which also helped them become more capable of taking part in local and national development initiatives. A highly helpful platform for integrating rural women into development practices was the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS: 2003-2007). In order to achieve its developmental objectives, NEEDS included the private sector, non-governmental organizations, and the general public. It was also replicated at all levels of government (State Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy, or SEEDS, and Local Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy, or LEEDS). NEEDS aspired to eradicate rural poverty and advance the development of rural space through the agency of women by working to empower the rural population, including women. These small successes in promoting women's involvement in rural development are quite recent, as the research makes clear. There are still a number of obstacles preventing women from fully participating in rural development initiatives. These factors are covered in the next section.

The Challenges for Integrating Women in Rural Development Agenda

Rural women are important and potential change agents in rural areas because of their role in resource management and household duties. Participating in agricultural and animal husbandry and production, providing food, water, and fuel for the family, as well as other livelihood tasks, are just a few of the diverse experiences that rural women manage on a daily basis. Their efforts and contributions are seldom mainstreamed in Nigerian national and local development policies and practices, and their voices are rarely heard in spite of these contributions. At whatever stage of development, a number of obstacles work against its mainstreaming and integration. Unfavourable cultural traditions, insufficient institutional and governmental frameworks for capacity building, a lack of rural infrastructure, a lack of awareness, restricted access to social networks and opportunities, etc. are some of these.

a. Cultural Tradition's Effect on Women's Involvement in Rural Development

It is impossible to view Nigerian rural women as a monolith. Age, class, marital status, ethnicity, race, and religion are all significant factors. In rural communities and homes, the division of labour between men and women is ingrained in respect to agricultural and other occupations. In terms of opportunities to participate in income-generating activities, this tends to discriminate against women (and girls). Women typically handle the majority of household chores and are less inclined to participate in decision-making, particularly when it comes to matters outside the family. Nigerian rural women are left to do a lot of household chores, such as childcare, food preparation, animal care, and cleaning, and they may also have to deal with daily challenges related to domestic water supply and farm work. In Nigeria, almost all of the work done by rural women is done for free. Women have less time for self-improvement and job goals as a result of these established roles. It has been established that the biggest obstacle facing rural women is cultural tradition. "All women in rural areas have a busy and unceasing day which starts in the early hours of morning, even before sunrise, and they are the last to retire to bed at night," claim Kaur and Sharma (2011: 13). Furthermore, most household tasks are completed by hand with little to no mechanical assistance. The operational space contexts influence the rural women's experiences. The convergence of custom and religion in Rivers State, as well as in Nigeria, makes women's status in relation to development issues more difficult. Every traditional ideological structure assign woman a secondary role. As seen by the prevalence of large-scale female traders, women enjoyed far greater social and economic freedom in many southern countries. Nevertheless, they were rarely given substantial political authority, a pattern that the state still follows today.

The basic patriarchal structure of Nigerian society, which appears to concentrate a great deal of power, wealth, privileges, and prestige in men over women, is reflected in several gender-based power positions. Women's various roles in society, such as "homemaker" status, inferior marital partners, and restricted access to social, economic, and political spheres, are manifestations of how they are viewed and treated

culturally. When the boundaries are crossed, these constrictive statuses and positions are enforced by various forms of social stereotypes and penalties. These prevent women from openly and actively taking part in programs for rural development. They may be working in the background, but their voices are never heard. Unless they have male offspring, women are typically not given much access to their deceased husband's benefits. One tactic used by women to subvert some barriers of dominance in the married family is to place a strong emphasis on the male offspring.

b. Critical Infrastructure Access

A significant obstacle to the status of rural women is the lack of fundamental social, economic, and physical infrastructure. Rural women are severely disadvantaged because they lack essential infrastructures like telephones, a good road network, power supply services, and water and sanitation facilities. Poor access to water resources, for example, exposes women to daily efforts to get water for domestic usages, given the traditional role of women in managing domestic resources and activities. Women typically devote a significant portion of their time and money to daily water supply, according to several studies (Akpabio 2018). Nigerian rural women rarely have access to contemporary domestic amenities that would improve household productivity and free up a significant amount of labour for other purposes. The majority of their farm and household tasks are done by hand with crude implements. There is no access to basic education in home economics management. Rural women's average home productivity may increase if they had access to contemporary domestic technologies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The inclusion of some international resolutions and agendas, as well as their subsequent domestication at the national government levels, including Nigeria, have highlighted the significance of women in development. The following suggestions are made in the report to enhance women's involvement in rural development:

a. Creating robust institutional support for gender mainstreaming is an urgent priority. Nigeria hasn't done much to domesticate pertinent international agenda items through local laws. Almost every facet of gender and women's development difficulties, such as property inheritance, violence and other types of abuse against women, universal education, and gender equality, are also affected by this challenge. Many of the current programs and initiatives are administrative decrees that hardly ever survive regime transitions. Right now, achieving the foundational empowerment of the current generation through high-quality education for girls and economic empowerment for women in general continues to be a crucial governmental objective. It is imperative that girl education be streamlined within the legal framework and made mandatory, with suitable sanctions for parents and guardians who fail to enroll their children.

b. Roads, operational schools, hospitals, markets, and credit systems are all lacking in rural areas in Nigeria. Rural women are still mostly employed in agriculture, and their organization is based on subsistence. Any attempts to increase the capabilities of rural women are undermined by the lack of basic infrastructure. Traditional obstacles, such as the lack of inheritance and proprietary rights, gender prejudice in opportunity access, etc., exacerbate the lack of essential infrastructures. Rural development should be a top priority for policymakers, and there should be essential infrastructure in place to link rural women to metropolitan markets and opportunities. These will undoubtedly result in significant empowerment and capacity building for rural women, putting them in a position to make valuable contributions to the development of rural areas.

c. Cultural and Religious Barriers: Nigerian rural women continue to face significant cultural barriers, such as status discrimination, preference for male children over female children, limited roles as "home makers" and domestic managers, and the "women in purdah phenomenon," which is prevalent among Muslim women. Women suffer from poverty, lack of empowerment, and abuse of all kinds as a result of these obstacles. Bold policy, legal, legislative, and administrative measures, as well as reforms, are necessary to remove these obstacles. This ought to constitute a pressing priority for policy deliberation.

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